

The enigmatic interna: Unravelling the intricacies of parasitic barnacles and their host's internal environment

Hailey Wang

BASIS International School

hailey.xy.wang@gmail.com

Abstract. Parasites are important to study as they help us understand diseases of organisms and find corresponding treatments. While there are many diseases associated with crustaceans, rhizocephalans, or parasitic barnacles, are one of the most peculiar problems of decapods, which is known as crabs. Their features including their life cycle, host manipulation, evolution is all very different from what have been known now. In this study, we used fluorescent staining to evaluate the histological structures of interna of parasitic barnacles. From the study, we have discovered that the parasitic barnacle interna does not grow through all the organs and tissues within the host; Besides, we also concluded that parasitic barnacle interna is hollow and it has a tube-like structure; Moreover, infected crabs appear to be significantly different from normal crabs. Hence, these tells us that the features of parasitic barnacles are extremely different from other types of barnacles, reflecting rhizocephalans' uniqueness.

1. Introduction

Rhizocephalans, a group of parasitic barnacles, have captivated researchers and naturalists for their unique lifestyles and intricate ecological relationships. The life cycle of parasitic barnacles is remarkably complex compared to their free-living counterparts: the female cypris larva turns into a sac-like egg attached to its host, which is a crab, entering its mature state while the male larva stays in its immature form, injecting sperm in the externa of the rhizocephalan when the egg grows to adult size [1]. Why are they so special?

Our vision is to observe parasitic barnacle interna in order to understand parasitic barnacle's peculiarities. Fluorescent staining is used in the study. This article explains the results of three specific focuses of parasitic barnacles on decapods: 1. Whether the interior area of parasitic barnacles is hollow; 2. Whether parasitic barnacles would spread through the whole interna of the host, including muscular tissues; 3. The differences between infected crabs and uninfected crabs.

2. Method

Our sample crabs were collected in Hong Kong Ocean Park and coastal area next to The University of Hong Kong Swire Institute of Marine Science (SWIMS). Infected crabs were found in SWIMS because the coastline at that location might be a hot spot where parasitic barnacles reproduce; uninfected crabs were found around Ocean Park.

An infected male crab (22.244216.114.166079) was dissected and separated into different body parts including its digestive glands, gills, claws and legs. The body part samples were then put in test tubes. To fix the samples, 4% of paraformaldehyde in seawater was used. After 48 hours, the samples, pipettes, pipette pump and fluorescent stains, which are DAPI, Phalloidin and Nile Red, were taken out (DAPI: dyes nuclei DNA; Phalloidin: dyes muscular tissues; Nile Red: dyes lipid droplets). In the experiment, 1 μ g/mL of DAPI, 1 μ g/mL of Phalloidin and 1 μ g/mL Nile Red were put in each test tube with the samples.

The samples were taken to fluorescent microscope and observed the stained parts under the microscope overnight. We ultimately took photos of the samples under the fluorescent microscope with 4x, 10x and 40x lens.

3. Results

3.1 Histological structures of interna

Under the microscope with Nile Red, we found that the interna of parasitic barnacle seemed to be translucent as some of the tubes are overlapping and are not completely filled with fluorescent signal in Figure 1A. However, this still couldn't prove that the interna of parasitic barnacle is hollow. Therefore, we observed the sample through the microscope with DAPI.

Under the microscope with DAPI in Figure 1B, we were able to see the fluorescent signals of the tubes of parasitic barnacle interna. The signals around marginal areas of the tube-like structure are where most signals gather. Moreover, the overlapping part of the parasitic barnacle in the centre of the image allows us to see through the tubes that are covered up.

Figure 1: Shows the interna of parasitic barnacle with Nile Red and DAPI. **A:** presents the fat of the parasitic barnacle interna with some oil droplets. **B:** presents the signals of the parasitic barnacle interna gathering around marginal areas of the parasitic barnacle tubes and overlapping in the centre of the image.

3.2 Unique muscle system of interna and interna distribution of interna in the host

From all other samples such as the infected crabs' leg muscles, gills and claw muscles, interna tissue was not founded under the fluorescence microscope; However, parasitic barnacles emerged in a large quantity when it comes to the infected crabs' hepatopancreas (digestive glands) in Figure 2A. This implies that the parasitic barnacle interna would only grow at specific organs of the host rather than spread through all the organs and tissues of the host. Figure 2B and Figure 2C show the enlargement of the host's digestive glands and parasitic barnacle interna around the host's digestive glands, proving that parasitic barnacle interna grows through the host's digestive glands. Under Phalloidin stain, interna tissue of parasitic barnacle shows very unique staining pattern as it is a star-like structure (Figure 2C). This is important as the structure might be a significant factor for parasitic barnacles interna to gain and move nutrition, and this links to the pattern of interna distribution in the host. Furthermore, Figure 2C also shows signals around marginal area of the tubes, supporting our speculation that parasitic barnacle interna is hollow.

Figure 2: Present images with Phalloidin staining pattern in a host crab's hepatopancreas (digestive glands) and interna. **A:** an overview of parasitic barnacle interna entangling digestive glands of the host. **B:** presents yellow dotted line highlighted area in A, showing Phalloidin staining pattern of digestive glands. **C:** red dotted line highlighted area in A.

3.3 Differences in histological structures of host tissue and interna

There are some important differences and similarity between infected and uninfected crabs. In Figure 3A and 3B, it shows that infected crabs have sac-like structure, which is the externa of parasitic barnacle, under their tails while uninfected crabs do not. This brings up the next difference: infected crabs have parasitic barnacle interna around their hepatopancreas while uninfected crabs do not. On the contrary, Figure 3C and Figure 3D show the muscular tissues of an infected and an uninfected crab, which are similar and have no big difference. This reflects that the muscular tissues remain the same after a crab became infected.

To further prove the statement that parasitic barnacle interna grows only around the host's digestive glands, Figure 3C and Figure 3D present the muscular tissues of an infected and an uninfected crab, which are similar to each other, meaning that no parasitic barnacle interna grows around the muscular tissues.

Figure 3: Shows the appearances and the Phalloidin staining patterns of claw muscle of an infected and an uninfected crab. **A:** an infected sample crab. **B:** an uninfected sample crab. **C:** the infected crab's muscular tissue. **D:** presents the uninfected crab's muscular tissue.

4. Discussion

Based on the results we found, one thing that is interesting to be aware of is that why the parasitic barnacle interna only grow through the digestive glands of the host. Differ from traditional view, the parasitic barnacle interna only grow around hepatopancreas rather than also spread to muscular tissues of the host. Muscular tissues are often used by crabs for movement such as catching prey or defencing themselves. If the parasitic barnacle interna grows around muscular tissues of the host, it would strongly interrupt the host's movement, which might threaten the host's life and thus the rhizocephalans. Another reason would be that crab's muscular tissues lack nutrients. Parasites often attach to the nutritious body part of the host such as the hepatopancreas so that they can flourish and grow. Besides, during the experiment, we have discovered that some infected crabs did not have the parasitic barnacle externa. This means that the number of infected crabs is way more than we expected.

The muscle elements of parasitic barnacles are also very interesting as they are in star-like structures shown in Figure 2C. The star-like structures might be a key for parasitic barnacle interna to function properly as they might be like a sucker attaching to the host's digestive glands and absorbing its nutrition. These patterns may mean that parasitic barnacles interna contract and transfer nutrients from the host through the small hollow lumen.

5. Conclusion

Parasitic barnacles maintain enigmatic to us as we only have superficial knowledge on this species. Through the three aims of this study, it further indicates that the evolution of parasitic barnacles is peculiar and unexpected, which might help us find its significant connections with the ecosystem if new discoveries of parasitic barnacles emerge.

References:

[1] Khor Waiho, F. M. (2020). Aquaculture. , Rhizocephalans and their potential impact on crustacean aquaculture. Malaysia: K. Waiho and H. Fazhan

Table 1: Record of body parts with parasitic barnacles

Sample types	Hepatopancreas	Leg muscles	Gills	Claw muscles
Infected male	Yes	N/A	N/A	N/A
Uninfected female	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
Infected male	Yes	N/A	N/A	N/A
Uninfected male	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A